

1 **The Xist-associated small NF90 (ILF3) associated RNAs, SNAR-As are activated during resistance**
2 **to chemotherapy in human breast cancer.**

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7 The non-coding RNA Xist functions in cancer through interactions with and modulation of the interleukin
8 enhancer factors ILF2 and ILF3. We previously described activation and repression of a suite of small
9 RNAs associated with ILF3 known as the Xist-associated small NF90 (ILF3) associated RNAs, or SNARs.
10 We report here that SNARs are activated in an in vitro model of chemotherapy resistance in triple negative
11 breast cancer. In response to exposure to both paclitaxel and doxorubicin, multiple SNARs including
12 SNAR-A4, SNAR-A14 and SNAR-A6 were transcriptionally activated in triple negative breast cancer cells
13 and this occurred concomitant with Xist activation. We discovered and described Xist activation or
14 silencing in response to p53 or Rb1 tumor suppressor impairment. Here we demonstrate that upon
15 deletion of Rb1 in cultured breast cancer cells (MCF7), SNARs including SNAR-A7 and SNAR-A11 are
16 silenced, and that this occurs concomitant with silencing of Xist. Together we conclude that SNARs are an
17 active species of small RNAs in breast cancer, are associated closely with Xist and the Xist-associated
18 factors ILF2 and ILF3, and become transcriptionally mobilized in response to exposure with chemotherapy
19 agents with differing mechanisms of action.
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